

Statement of Scientific Precedence Markoulakis E.N. *et al.* - Free Space and Dark Energy theorized as a Superluminal Oscillations' Tachyon Graviton Condensate medium (SGCV) at rest

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**The authors claim hereby and herein being the first ever historically and by timeline that have proposed and researched this topic and declare their right to be the first inline to receive any scientific and public recognition and awards in case their pioneering research proves correct and is validated in the future even after death.
Markoulakis E.N. *et al.* - 25 March 2025.**

References of Superluminal Dark Sector Research by Markoulakis *et al.* Free Space and Dark Energy theorized as a “Superluminal Oscillations’ Tachyon Graviton Condensate medium (SGCV) at rest”

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